

**COMMERCIAL BANKS AS A MAJOR PLAYER IN THE BUSINESS AND
FINANCIAL SECTOR****Bobojonov Khursand Kadamovich**

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If we pay attention to the activities of commercial banks in the international stock market, commercial banks participate in the stock market not only as issuers and investors, but also as financial intermediaries. In this way, commercial banks, in addition to directing their savings to the stock market, help to actively attract and redistribute the funds of the population and various investors to the stock market. "Banks, insurance companies and non-state pension funds, which are highlighted as strong institutional investors, offer relevant financial services, and also influence the investment environment in the country, are the main participants in investment activity." Therefore, increasing the activity of commercial banks in the stock market becomes relevant not only in national practice, but also in international practice.

In the world, various stock exchanges, central banks and other mega-regulators have conducted scientific research aimed at increasing the financial stability, profitability, mutual competition, liquidity and profitability of investments in securities, etc. in the regulation of stock markets and participants. . Although the issues of reducing risks, ensuring financial stability, and increasing liquidity related to the participation of commercial banks in the stock market have been studied in these studies, issues related to sudden changes in the prices of securities in the stock market, evaluation of the value of securities, and mediation activities in the stock market of commercial banks have been investigated. has not yet fully found its scientific solution. In particular, the existence of issues such as increasing the investment attractiveness of commercial banks through their participation in the stock market, regulating relations with investors in their dividend policy and interest policy, improving the intermediary activity of commercial banks, in particular, the underwriting activity, requires a number of scientific studies to be conducted in this regard.

"Commercial banks are the main players in the business and financial sector in the USA. In the US, commercial banks primarily serve businesses rather than individuals. Although banking revenues can fluctuate dramatically

depending on economic conditions, annual commercial banking revenues are projected to reach nearly \$490 billion in 2021. As of August 21, 2021, the total assets of US commercial banks are 17.49 billion. amounted to US dollars. The leading commercial bank in America is JP Morgan Chase, which earned more than \$142 billion in 2019."

Figure 1. The world's leading investment banks by the amount of income received from bonds in 2022

According to the data of Figure 1, in 2022, among the world's leading investment banks, JP Morgan will be 3045.1 mln. It led with USD, followed by BOFA Security Inc (USD 2,529.4 million), Citi (USD 2,092.4 million), Morgan Stanley (USD 1,816.1 million), Goldman Sachs & Co. (1735.4 million US dollars) was occupied by investment banks.

Figure 2. The world's leading investment banks by the amount of income received from shares in 2022

The data of Figure 2 shows the indicators of the world's leading investment banks by the amount of income received from shares in 2022, the highest result was shown by the investment bank Goldman Sachs & Co (US\$ 3222.2 million). Also like Morgan Stanley (USD 2656.18 million), JP Morgan (USD 2474.01 million), BOFA Security Inc (USD 1893.75 million), Citi (USD 1736.25 million) investment banks have earned higher returns on stocks.

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